

HausaMovieReview: A Manually Annotated Sentiment Dataset for Hausa Language NLP

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Abstract: The Hausa-language entertainment industry, particularly the rapidly expanding Kannywood sector, generates substantial viewer feedback across digital platforms, yet progress in Hausa NLP has been constrained by the lack of high-quality annotated datasets. This paper introduces HausaMovieReview, a manually annotated sentiment dataset of 5,000 YouTube comments selected from 17,095 viewer reactions to Kannywood movie episodes. The comments were cleaned, sampled, and independently annotated by three native Hausa speakers, achieving strong inter-annotator agreement (Fleiss' Kappa = 0.865), which confirms label reliability. The dataset covers three sentiment classes: positive, negative, and neutral, and supports sentiment analysis and opinion mining tasks. Baseline experiments using TF-IDF features show that Decision Tree achieved the highest accuracy (0.8971), while Logistic Regression produced the best AUC score (0.9592); KNN performed weakest overall. The dataset is publicly available to advance Hausa NLP research.

Keywords: Hausa, Kannywood, Low-Resource Languages, NLP, Sentiment Analysis

1. Introduction

Sentiment analysis is an essential task in natural language processing (NLP), enabling the automatic interpretation of opinions, attitudes and emotional expressions [1] within textual data. While substantial progress has been made for high resource languages such as English and Chinese, many African languages including Hausa lack annotated datasets necessary for building robust NLP tools. This shortage limits the development of applications such as recommender systems, automated feedback analysis and cultural analytics for Hausa-speaking communities.

The Kannywood film industry, representing largest Hausa-language entertainment sectors, generates massive engagement across online platforms, particularly YouTube [2]. Viewers actively express

opinions through comments, providing a rich but underexplored resource for understanding public sentiment. To address this gap, we introduce HausaMovieReview, a sentiment classification dataset sourced from 17,095 YouTube comments, with 5,000 manually annotated for sentiment polarity.

Unlike previous datasets, HausaMovieReview focuses specifically on the Kannywood domain and follows a transparent data collection and annotation methodology, making it a reproducible and domain-relevant resource for low-resource NLP research.

2. Related Work on Hausa NLP Datasets

The work on African language NLP has grown in recent years, available sentiment resources for Hausa are still relatively limited. NaijaSenti [3] introduced a large Nigerian Twitter sentiment corpus that includes Hausa and showed how pre-trained models and transfer learning can be effective in low-resource settings[4]. More recently, the work on AfriSenti-SemEval have extended sentiment classification to 14 African languages including Hausa by releasing about 110K sentiment-labeled tweets and demonstrating strong performance[5]. For more focused Hausa data [6] compiled over 40,000 Hausa student comments for sentiment classification, while [7] studied multilingual sentiment analysis on Hausa tweets using improved feature extraction techniques. However, these datasets are largely drawn from Twitter and educational feedback. To the best of our knowledge, there is no publicly available sentiment dataset dedicated to Hausa movie reviews from the Kannywood industry. The HausaMovieReview dataset is proposed to help fill this gap.

3. Methodology

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3.1 Dataset Description Data Source

The dataset consists of user-generated comments extracted from 11 episodes of the Hausa-language Kannywood series Labarina published on YouTube. The platform YouTube was selected as the primary data source due to several compelling factors that make it particularly suitable for sentiment analysis within the Hausa-language entertainment domain.

1) High Volume of Authentic, Spontaneous Viewer Opinions:

The platform hosts thousands of user-generated comments on Kannywood movie uploads, providing a naturally occurring corpus of viewer reactions. Unlike structured surveys or prompted feedback, YouTube comments are spontaneous and unfiltered, capturing genuine emotional responses, criticisms and appreciations. This abundance of real-world user interaction offers a rich environment for modeling natural sentiment expressions in Hausa. 2) Significant Hausa-Speaking User Base:

Kannywood content attracts a large and highly active Hausa-speaking audience from Nigeria, Niger, Ghana, Cameroon and the Hausa diaspora worldwide. This makes YouTube one of the most linguistically diverse and representative sources of Hausa digital discourse currently available. The consistent engagement from native speakers ensures that the collected comments reflect authentic language usage, including idiomatic expressions, dialectal variations and conversational structures unique to Hausa.

3) Comment Threads Rich in Emotion, Critique, Praise and Community Reactions:

YouTube's comment threads foster open community interaction, resulting in multi-layered sentiments that go beyond simple viewer feedback. Users often express excitement, disappointment, humor, religious sentiments and cultural reflections about Kannywood movies. In addition, viewers frequently respond to one another, creating conversational sentiment patterns that reveal collective attitudes. The emotional richness and diversity within these threads make them ideal for building a sentiment analysis dataset capable of capturing a broad spectrum of expressive nuances in Hausa.

A total of 17,095 raw comments were collected, forming the foundation from which the final dataset was curated.

YouTube Data Extraction Process

To ensure a systematic and reproducible data collection process, this study followed four major steps when extracting comments from YouTube using the YouTube Data API.

1) Creation of a Google Cloud Project

A dedicated project was created within the Google Cloud Console. This project provided the environment required for enabling APIs and managing authentication credentials used during data extraction.

2) Enabling the YouTube Data API v3

The YouTube Data API v3 was enabled through the Google Cloud API Library. The API provides

programmatic access to YouTube resources, including comment threads, video metadata and channel-level data. Enabling this service was necessary to retrieve comments related to the selected Kannywood movie episodes.

3) Generation of API Key Credentials

From the APIs & Services through the Credentials section of the Google Cloud Console, an API key was generated. This key served as the authentication token for all API requests executed during data extraction. It ensured that the Python-based extraction script could securely access the YouTube API. 4) Extraction of Comments Using a Python Script A Python script was developed using the to automate the extraction process. The script performed the following actions:

1. Accepted a predefined list of video IDs representing episodes of the Labarina series
2. Queried the YouTube API for both top-level comments and threaded replies
3. Extracted relevant metadata, including comment text, publication timestamp and author identifiers
4. Stored all retrieved comments and metadata in structured CSV files for subsequent preprocessing and annotation

This automated pipeline enabled efficient retrieval of 17,095 publicly available comments from YouTube, forming the raw corpus for the HausaMovieReview dataset.

Annotation

1. **Sampling:** Out of 17,095 collected comments, I selected 5,000 comments using uniform random sampling. Comments containing only emojis, non-text symbols or excessive code-switching were excluded to ensure annotatability.
2. **Annotators:** Three native Hausa speakers with strong familiarity with Kannywood content were engaged for annotation.
3. **Annotation Labels:** A three-class sentiment scheme was developed:

Table 1: Labeling Scheme

Label	Description	Example
Positive	Praise, approval, gratitude, admiration	"Gaskiya wannan film yayi kyau sosai"
Negative	Criticism, dislike, disappointment	"Banji dadin wannan episode ba"
Neutral	Factual, off-topic, ambiguous, questions	"Yaushe za a saki episode na gaba?"

Each annotator independently assigned one label per comment.

Annotation Guidelines

1. Before the annotation process commenced, all annotators underwent a structured training phase

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designed to ensure consistency and reliability in label assignment. The training materials included:

2. A detailed annotation guideline document, outlining sentiment categories, definitions and labeling rules.
3. A curated set of sample comments, each accompanied by the correct sentiment label and justification, to illustrate the application of the guidelines.
4. Clarification sessions on ambiguous and edge case scenarios, such as sarcasm, mixed or conflicting sentiments, religious expressions, rhetorical questions and culturally embedded idioms.

This preparatory phase ensured that all annotators shared a unified understanding of the sentiment categories, ultimately contributing to the high level of agreement observed across independent annotations.

Annotation Procedure

Each of the three trained annotators independently reviewed and labeled all 5,000 comments. The process followed these steps:

1. **Independent Label Assignment:** Annotators assigned one of the three sentiment labels Positive, Negative, or Neutral according to the predefined guidelines. No communication between annotators was permitted during this phase in order to prevent bias.
2. **Majority-Vote Label Resolution:** For each comment, the final label was determined through a simple majority rule. If at least two annotators agreed on a label, that label was assigned. In cases where all three annotators disagreed (rare occurrences), the comment was flagged for a resolution meeting.
3. **Consensus Resolution for Conflicts:** Comments with no initial majority agreement were discussed collectively by the annotators and the dataset coordinator. A consensus label was then assigned based on guideline interpretation and the contextual meaning of the comment.

This structured approach ensured both independence during the initial labeling and collaborative refinement when discrepancies occurred.

Final Label Assignment

A majority vote system was used:

If 2 or more annotators agreed → label accepted

If all 3 disagreed → group discussion ensued and final consensus was reached

This process ensured reliability and minimized subjective variability.

Statistics

Key dataset statistics are summarized below. The dataset exhibits natural, real-world class imbalance typical of user-generated content, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Sentiment Dataset Statistics

Metric	Value
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Total raw comments	17,095
Curated annotated dataset	5,000
Positive	2,840 (56.8%)
Neutral	995 (19.9%)
Negative	1,165 (23.3%)
Total annotators	3

Inter-Annotator Agreement

To validate the reliability and consistency of the annotation process, two key metrics were used to measure inter-annotator agreement (IAA): Cohen's Kappa (κ) and Fleiss' Kappa (κ). Cohen's Kappa measures pairwise agreement between two annotators, while Fleiss' Kappa extends this to measure the agreement among all three annotators. The resulting Fleiss' Kappa score of 0.865 indicates "Almost Perfect" agreement among the three annotators, according to the standard scale proposed (Landis & Koch, 2014). This high score is a testament to the clarity of the annotation guidelines and the quality of the dataset.

The scores obtained were provided in as demonstrated by the scores in Table 3. Also, Table 4 illustrates the high consistency in label distributions across all three annotators and the final Majority Vote distribution.

Table 3: Inter-Annotator Agreement Scores

Pair	Cohen's/Fleiss' Kappa
Annotator 1 vs Annotator 2	0.7975
Annotator 1 vs Annotator 3	0.9071
Annotator 2 vs Annotator 3	0.8903
Fleiss' Kappa (All Annotators)	0.865

Table 4: Annotator Label Distributions

Annotator	Negative %	Neutral %	Positive %
Annotator 1	1165(23.30)	996(19.92)	2839(56.80)
Annotator 2	1165(23.30)	995(19.90)	2840(56.80)
Annotator 3	1165(23.30)	995(19.90)	2840(56.80)
Majority Vote	1165(23.30)	995(19.90)	2840(56.80)

These high IAA scores are a testament to the quality of the dataset and the clarity of the annotation guidelines, ensuring that the HausaMovieReview dataset is a robust and trustworthy resource for sentiment analysis research. The complete dataset and all associated code are publicly available on GitHub.

<https://github.com/AsiyaZanga/HausaMovieReview.git>

3.2 Classical Machine Learning Models Used Dataset Splits, Label Encoding and Reproducibility

To enable reproducibility, three key experimentation stages were followed: label encoding, dataset splitting and controlled oversampling.

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First, the sentiment categories (Positive, Neutral, Negative) were converted into numerical representations using a LabelEncoder. The assigned values were: Negative = 0, Neutral = 1 and Positive = 2. This encoding scheme was consistently maintained throughout the experiments, ensuring uniform interpretation of labels by all models.

Following encoding, the dataset was divided using a 70/30 stratified train/test split, meaning that 70% of the samples were used for model training while the remaining 30% formed the test set. Stratification was applied to preserve the original class proportions during splitting. Model evaluation was further strengthened through 10-fold cross-validation, performed exclusively on the training portion. This ensured that the reported metrics reflect model stability across multiple training cycles rather than a single train-test run.

Because the raw dataset was imbalanced with Positive sentiment occurring notably more frequently, the training set underwent a class balancing stage. Importantly, this was done only after the data had been split and only on the training portion, so that the test set remained untouched and representative of real-world sentiment distribution. Oversampling was achieved by duplicating instances of the minority classes (Negative and Neutral) until all three sentiment groups were approximately balanced for model learning. By isolating oversampling to the training data, we avoided information leakage and ensured that final performance scores reflected generalization rather than exposure to duplicated patterns.

In summary, labels were encoded numerically, the dataset was split using a stratified 70/30 partition, model evaluation relied on 10-fold cross-validation and oversampling was strictly limited to the training subset to mitigate class imbalance while maintaining realistic evaluation conditions.

Feature Extraction

Classical models require numerical input, so the text comments were transformed using TF-IDF. This method highlights words that are important within a specific comment while reducing the influence of commonly occurring terms. A maximum of 5,000 features was used to control dimensionality.

Classical Learning Models

Three traditional machine learning classifiers were used to provide baseline results:

1. **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN):** Classifies a comment by looking at the most common label among its nearest neighbors.
2. **Decision Tree (DT):** Builds a set of simple decision rules that split the data into groups until each group represents a sentiment class.
3. **Logistic Regression (LR):** A linear model that predicts sentiment by estimating class probabilities. It works well with high dimensional TF-IDF features.

Evaluation Method and Metrics

Model performance was assessed using Repeated Stratified 10-Fold Cross-Validation and later confirmed with a separate 30% test set. Five standard metrics were used: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score and AUC. Macro-averaging ensured that each sentiment class contributed equally to the final results.

4. Results and Discussion

To establish a strong baseline for sentiment classification, the classical models were trained using TF-IDF features and evaluated through Repeated Stratified 10-Fold Cross-Validation. Before training, the dataset imbalance was addressed by oversampling the Negative and Neutral classes to ensure equal representation. The macro-averaged performance metrics for these models are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Model Performance for Classical Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC
Decision Tree	0.8971	0.9002	0.8971	0.896	0.9345
KNN	0.6336	0.7689	0.6336	0.6211	0.8627
Logistic Regression	0.8681	0.8708	0.8681	0.8681	0.9592

Table 5 summarizes the performance of the three classical models. The Decision Tree produced the best overall results, achieving the highest accuracy (0.8971) and strong scores across all other metrics. Logistic Regression also performed very well, recording the highest AUC value (0.9592) which indicates excellent ability to distinguish between sentiment classes. In contrast, KNN performed the weakest, with significantly lower accuracy, F1-score and AUC.

The robustness and stability of the models across the 10 folds are further visualized in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively.

Figure 1: Accuracy of KNN, Logistic Regression and Decision Tree Models Across 10 Folds

Figure 1 illustrates the macro-averaged accuracy of the Decision Tree, Logistic Regression and KNN models across 10 folds of cross-validation. It demonstrates that the Decision Tree and Logistic Regression models maintain consistently higher and more stable accuracy (generally

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above 0.85) compared to the KNN model, which performs significantly lower and is less stable.

Figure 2: F1 Score of KNN, Logistic Regression and Decision Tree Models Across 10 Folds

Figure 2 displays the macro-averaged F1-Score of the Decision Tree, Logistic Regression and KNN models across 10 cross-validation folds. The plot confirms the pattern established by accuracy, showing that DT and LR achieve superior, stable performance, while the distance-based KNN model's F1-score remains substantially lower.

Figure 3: AUC Score of KNN, Logistic Regression and Decision Tree Models Across 10 Folds

Figure 3 presents the Area Under the Curve (AUC) score for all three classical models over 10 folds. It highlights that Logistic Regression consistently achieves the highest AUC, followed closely by the Decision Tree, confirming that both linear and tree-based models are more effective at distinguishing between sentiment classes than the volatile KNN model.

Model Comparison

The accuracy, F1-score and AUC plots across the 10 folds show a consistent pattern. Decision Tree and Logistic Regression remain stable and high. KNN fluctuates and stays far below the other two models.

Overall, the results indicate that tree-based and linear models handle Hausa sentiment classification more effectively than distance-based methods like KNN.

Analysis of Optimal Model Performance.

The superior performance of the Decision Tree (DT, highest Accuracy) and Logistic Regression (LR, highest AUC) over the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model is a crucial finding that validates the feature engineering approach. Their success can be attributed to their distinct mechanisms for handling the high-dimensional, sparse feature space generated by TF-IDF:

Decision Tree (DT) Success: The DT's non-linear, rule-based operation is highly effective at exploiting the structure of sentiment in the Hausa data. Its high accuracy suggests that sentiment is largely determined by a limited number of highly discriminative keywords. The DT finds the optimal non-linear thresholds (splits) on these TF-IDF feature weights, allowing it to isolate specific, powerful sentiment terms and classify the comment based on a set of simple, effective rules. This rule-based approach is inherently robust against noise and generalized, neutral terms, mitigating the distance-based misclassifications observed in KNN.

Logistic Regression (LR) Success: The LR model's top AUC score highlights its excellent ability to distinguish and rank sentiment classes. While LR is a linear classifier, operating on the 5,000-dimensional TF-IDF feature space provides it with sufficient power to find an optimal separating hyperplane. The ability to assign unique, optimized weights to every sentiment-carrying token in the feature space allows LR to effectively capture the cumulative signal of complex comments. The high AUC confirms that the probabilistic confidence scores outputted by LR are reliable, indicating strong class separation across various thresholds.

Collectively, the strong results from both DT and LR validate the TF-IDF feature engineering methodology. Their success demonstrates that sentiment in this domain is strongly correlated with the unique frequency and presence of specific words, making the selected features highly informative for both rule-based and linear classification algorithms.

Qualitative Error Analysis

To complement the overall performance metrics and to better understand where the models encountered difficulties, a qualitative error analysis was conducted on the misclassified samples from the unseen test set. Table 6 presents the common misclassification patterns observed in the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model which recorded the lowest accuracy among all the classifiers evaluated.

Table 6: Qualitative Analysis of KNN Misclassification (Slowest performing model)

True Label	Predicted Label	Original Text	Example Text	Analysis and Discussion Point

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	d L a b e l			
Posi tive	N e u t r a l	7	'Allah sarki Maryam kawar kirkii 🤍🥹'	Emoji/Prayer Ambiguity: The comment contains clear praise (kawar kirkii - 'good friend'), but the inclusion of generalized prayer terms (Allah sarki) and the emotional context (crying emoji 🥹) dilute the overall feature vector. KNN struggles to prioritize the sentiment keywords, causing the instance to drift toward the dense 'Neutral' cluster.
Ne gat ive	N e g a t i v e	132	'Amma gaskiya daractan nan bai san aikin chiba'	Explicit Criticism/Negation: This translates to "The director really doesn't know their job." Despite the explicit negative sentiment, the model fails to pull the instance away from the 'Neutral' mass. This indicates that the individual TF-IDF weights for specific Hausa negative phrases are not strong enough to be discriminative in KNN's distance calculation.
Ne utr al	N e g a t i v e	2597	'Kai saira yadai 🥹🥹🥹🥹'	Emotional Cue Overload: The text itself is a neutral inquiry ("What's up, Saira?"). However, the strong presence of multiple crying emojis (🥹🥹🥹🥹) is interpreted by the distance-based model as proximity to highly emotional content. This non-textual cue overrides the textual neutrality, pulling the classification toward Negative.

The findings show that KNN struggles with short Hausa comments, especially when the text contains emojis, prayer expressions or negation forms. These elements make the sentiment less clear and the TF-IDF features do not capture them well. As a result, the model often pushes such comments toward the Neutral or sometimes Negative class. Because KNN mainly depends on simple word matching and does not account for context, it easily misses the emotional markers and emphasis that are common in everyday Hausa writing.

Conclusion

This paper introduces HausaMovieReview, a manually annotated sentiment dataset designed to advance sentiment analysis for the Hausa language. By systematically collecting, cleaning, sampling and annotating 5,000 comments from 17,095 YouTube posts, the dataset fills a critical gap in low-resource NLP. The detailed annotation guidelines, high inter-annotator agreement and public availability ensure that HausaMovieReview will serve as a foundational resource for developing modern NLP tools tailored to Hausa. This dataset paves the way for improved sentiment analysis, cultural analytics and domain specific applications within Kannywood and the broader Hausa digital ecosystem.

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